

Getting to the Heart of the Matter: Infective Endocarditis Caused by *Abiotrophia defectiva* – A Case Series

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Abstract:

Abiotrophia defectiva is a rare cause of infective endocarditis (IE). It is formidable to diagnose due to the gradual presentation of the disease and the organism's fastidious nature. These fastidious pathogens are extremely important even if they are uncommon since they have been linked to an increased risk of morbidity and mortality. Consequently, it is critical to understand the variety of clinical manifestations and crucial factors to consider when managing individuals with atypical microorganism-associated infective endocarditis. Here, we present a case series involving two different clinical presentations of prosthetic valve and native valve endocarditis with *Abiotrophia defectiva*. Even with recent advances, managing IE is still a difficult and complex issue. Patients with endocarditis need more accurate clinical evaluation along with accurate identification of etiological agents and appropriate antimicrobial therapy.

Keywords: *Abiotrophia defectiva*, Infective endocarditis, Nutritionally variant streptococci, Case series, Satellitism.

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Introduction

Infective endocarditis (IE) is a chronic infection of the lining or valves of the heart that is mainly bacterial in origin, which can be either culture positive or negative. [1]The primary causes of infective endocarditis are viridans streptococci, which include several species. As normal inhabitants of the oral cavity, they enter the bloodstream as a result of gingivitis, periodontitis, or dental manipulation.

Heart valves, especially those that have been previously damaged, are convenient surfaces for the attachment of these bacteria. *Streptococcus sanguinis* and *Streptococcus mutans* are commonly isolated from patients with streptococcal endocarditis. Other causes of infective endocarditis are HACEK group, *Haemophilus* spp., *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, *Cardiobacterium hominis*, *Eikenella corrodens*, *Kingella kingae*, Enterococci, Coagulase-negative Staphylococci, *Coxiella burnetti*, *Bartonella* species, *Candida* species and culture-negative species. [1]

Staphylococcus epidermidis and other coagulase-negative staphylococci have been increasingly implicated as the cause of infection associated with

intravascular catheters. Here, we present two cases of infective endocarditis caused by *Abiotrophia defectiva*. Although it is rare, it causes high mortality and morbidity for patients.

Case 1

A 54-year-old male was admitted with cough for one and a half months and fever for 20 days. He was well one and a half months ago. The cough was dry and worsened when supine and talking.

The fever, low-grade with an evening rise, lasted 20 days and was relieved by medication. He had similar symptoms two years ago that resolved with treatment. He had type 2 diabetes mellitus, treated with oral hypoglycaemic agents for 3 years. He smoked for 10 years and was a chronic alcoholic for 15 years. Examination revealed grade 2 clubbing, a pulse rate of 82/min, and weak left upper limb pulse. Blood pressure in the upper and lower limbs were 100/40 mmHg and 150/60 mmHg, respectively. A Grade 2 ejection systolic murmur was present in the aortic area without carotid radiation.

Investigations showed a normal electrocardiogram, normal left ventricle systolic function, and a dilated

left ventricle with a bicuspid aortic valve on transthoracic echocardiography. A 1.2 cm x 0.9 cm vegetation was attached to the aortic valve, causing moderate to severe aortic regurgitation. Infective endocarditis (IE) was suspected, and three paired blood samples were collected for culture before starting antibiotics. All six blood culture bottles were positive within 17-19 hours. Gram staining and subculture from blood culture broth revealed Gram-positive cocci in chains. MALDI-TOF-MS identified *Abiotrophia defectiva* with a confidence score of 99.9%, while *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* and *Micrococcus spp.* were isolated from the remaining bottles.

The clinical team was advised to starting penicillin/vancomycin and gentamicin. The patient was treated with ceftriaxone and gentamicin, becoming afebrile within a week and was advised to undergo valve replacement.

Case 2

A 49-year-old male with rheumatic heart disease post-mitral valve replacement, on regular medication, was admitted with breathlessness, dizziness, and vomiting for 10 days. He was well 10 days prior. Breathlessness was not associated with lower limb swelling or facial fullness. He had 5-6 non-bilious vomiting episodes per day, low-grade intermittent fever without chills or rigors,

agitation, and decreased sleep for the last 5 days. He had similar complaints for the past 7 months and had undergone mitral valve replacement in 2012. He also had coronary artery disease on regular medication for 12 years, type 2 diabetes mellitus on oral hypoglycemic agents for 5 months, Bell's palsy, a history of CVA, and head trauma 3 months prior. NCCT revealed intraparenchymal haemorrhage in the right Baso frontal region, subarachnoid haemorrhage, and prominent ventricles. He was also an alcoholic.

Examination showed a pulse rate of 86 beats/min, regular rhythm, and blood pressure of 96/84 mm Hg. An ejection systolic murmur was present in the aortic area. Fundus examination revealed papilledema, Roth spots, and splinter haemorrhages in both eyes, and branched retinal vessel occlusion in the left eye. Investigations showed a normal electrocardiogram. Transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) revealed well-moving mitral valve prosthesis with no mitral valve regurgitation, mild aortic regurgitation, and trivial tricuspid regurgitation. Left ventricle systolic function was normal with no regional wall motion abnormalities or vegetation. Transoesophageal echocardiography (TEE) showed 9 mm x 9 mm nodular vegetation in the right coronary and noncoronary cusps of the aortic valve.

Table 1: Time to positivity of the blood culture

Cases	Bottle Number*	TTP (hours)	Gram stain	MALDI TOF identification
Case 1	1	17	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	2	17.10	Gram-positive cocci in clusters	<i>Staphylococcus hemolyticus</i>
	3	18.30	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	4	17.80	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	5	17.60	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	6	19.30	Gram-positive cocci in clusters	<i>Micrococcs luteus</i>
Case 2	1	14.90	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	2	15.20	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	3	15.10	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	4	14	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	5	14.80	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>
	6	14.60	Gram-positive cocci in long chains	<i>Abiotrophia defectiva</i>

* As per the modified Duke's criteria 6 blood culture samples are recommended.

Figure 1: Satellitism of *Abiotrophia defectiva* on 5% sheep blood agar

Figure 2: Gram -stained smear showing Gram-positive cocci in chains

Discussion

In 1961, Frenkle and Hirsh made the first discovery of nutritionally variable streptococci (NVSs), also known as *Abiotrophia defectiva*, in a patient with subacute infective endocarditis. Over the following years, the names of these microorganisms underwent numerous changes. Following the use of DNA–DNA hybridization tests that showed that NVS were taxonomically separate from the other viridans group of organisms to which they were previously associated, Bouvet et al. proposed the names *Streptococcus defectivus* and *Streptococcus adjacens* in 1989.

In 1995, Kawamura and colleagues examined the 16S rRNA (rRNA) sequences of these two species. The species were determined through analysis to be unrelated to the *Streptococcus* genus. The authors suggested naming these bacteria *A. adjacens* and *A. defectiva*, which belong to the new genus *Abiotrophia*. Later, a number of other species, including *A. balaenopterae* and *A. paraadjacens*, were discovered. Based on the 16S rRNA heterogeneity and observed phenotypic differences, Collins and Lawson advocated the reclassification of all *Abiotrophia* species—aside from *A. defectiva*—into the new genus *Granulicatella* in 2000. Typically, *Granulicatella* species are isolated from immunocompromised animals, and *A. defectiva* is isolated from immunocompetent hosts. [2]

Abiotrophia defectiva is a nutritional variant of *Streptococcus*, as it requires vitamin B6 (a pyridoxol-dependent *Streptococcus*) for its growth in culture media. These species are unable to multiply without the addition of 0.001% pyridoxal hydrochloride (also called thiol or vitamin B6).

However, human blood introduced into blood culture media provides enough pyridoxal to allow organisms to multiply in bottles, and standard sheep blood agar plates may not support their growth. Subculturing the broth to a 5% sheep blood agar plate and either overlaying a streak of *Staphylococcus aureus* or dropping a pyridoxal disk to produce the supplement generally allows colonies of the streptococci to grow as tiny satellites next to the streak, showing satellitism. Usually, they are either alpha-hemolytic or nonhemolytic. [3]

The oral cavity is where *A. defectiva* is most frequently isolated; however, it can also be detected in the genitourinary and intestinal systems. *A. defectiva* has been found to colonize healthy people's mouths at a rate of 11.8%, and it typically enters the bloodstream through these portals. NVS are responsible for 3% to 5% of cases of IE linked to streptococci. *A. defectiva* is a rare but significant cause of blood culture-negative IE. Exopolysaccharide secretion and fibronectin

adhesion provide evidence for the special predilection of *A. defectiva* for endovascular tissue. [4]The primary risk factors for this organism causing endocarditis include any recent dental procedures, preexisting cardiac conditions, artificial heart valves, antibiotic medication, and excessive alcohol use. [5] Gupta *et al.* reported the first case of simultaneous infection of both the mitral and aortic valves caused by *Abiotrophia defectiva* from an Indian patient with congenital bicuspid aortic stenosis and had a history of balloon aortic valvotomy of the bicuspid aortic valve who was treated with ceftriaxone and gentamicin and became afebrile after 2 days of treatment. [6]

Similarly, Bozkurt *et al.* reported the case of a 42-year-old woman who previously had rheumatic heart disease and presented with symptoms of fever and chills. Following antimicrobial therapy and surgical intervention, including aorta and mitral valve replacement, the patient recovered. [7]Thus, when atypical symptoms are present, *A. defectiva* should be considered a causative organism of endocarditis. A PubMed search using the terms '*Abiotrophia*' and 'Case reports' revealed 152 results. Among these results, *Abiotrophia* has been reported to cause prosthetic joint septic arthritis, endophthalmitis, cardioembolic stroke, liver abscess, glomerulonephritis, spondylodiscitis, and tubo-ovarian abscess. [8] It has been linked to the etiology of culture-negative endocarditis and is estimated to be the causative organism of 5-6% of endocarditis cases. Among these reports, 104 were reports of *Abiotrophia* causing endocarditis, most of which were in patients with valvular pathology (90%) or with prosthetic valves (10%). There is a high preponderance of the aortic and mitral valves. Compared to endocarditis caused by streptococci, NVS endocarditis is more dangerous and fatal with a fatality rate of 9.2%. [9] Its clinical progression is typically slow. There is a high prevalence of resistance to beta-lactams (50%) and macrolides (93%). [10] This is mainly due to the production of large amounts of exopolysaccharides.

Conclusion

IE caused by *Abiotrophia defectiva* is associated with increased mortality and relapse. Thus, the atypical clinical presentation of *Abiotrophia defectiva* has to be kept in mind as it is an emerging pathogen and timely identification and antibiotic therapy might be helpful in reducing the mortality and morbidity of the patient. Prompt imaging evaluation and surgical intervention should be scheduled to avoid late complications.

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